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Leadership Attitude of office Heads toward Employees and Leadership Styles

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Abstract. The objective of the study was to investigate the effect of leadership attitude toward employees and the leadership styles practiced by the office heads. To establish the theoretical foundation of the study, related literature was reviewed. The study used a descriptive correlational research design and the questionnaires were used to gather the data. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to interpret the data. Weighted mean was used to determine the level of leadership attitude and leadership styles. Pearson r correlation was used to determine the correlation between the leadership attitude and the leadership styles of office heads. As a whole, the leadership attitude of office heads toward employees was high (4.18) and the leadership styles were moderate (3.46). Overall, the study found that there is no correlation between leadership attitude toward employees and leadership styles of office head and therefore the hypothesis of the study is rejected.

Keywords. Leadership attitude, leadership styles, cognitive, affective, laissez-faire

I. Introduction

Leading people in an organization is not just about influencing or motivating people through one's skills or knowledge, though it is important, it is not everything. Talking about leadership is not all about the strategy such as vision-mission, objectives, key result areas, performance indicators and strategies, and courage to lead. Or it does not limit to action such as decision making, communication, mobilizing others. It is also not limited to delivering the results which require risk-taking, agility, and result focus (Barberry & Greaves, 2012). Though they are needed leadership involves more than risk-taking, strategy, action, and result, it also involves the right attitude toward the problems, the work, the organization, and the employees who are working for the organization. Leaders' attitude toward these things may influence the way how he/she deals with them. Leaders can have both attitudes, positive and negative, and both influence his/her behavior on how he/she will deal with the problems, the work, the organization, and the employees.

The current study brings us back to the theory X and Y (McGregor (1960) and theory Z (Ouchi, 1981). The theories provides three different ways of how one leads or manages an organization. The way how one leads and manages to depend on how one views or perceives his/her employees (Stanwick & Stanwick, 2020). On one hand, theory X views employees as lazy

people, lack ambition, seeking security and economic need, and do not like work, and therefore they must be coerced, controlled, directed, and threatened with punishment (McGregor, 1960). On the other hand, theory Y looks at employees positively. This theory argues that work is just natural and therefore workers will exercise self-direction and are committed to achieving the objective (McGregor, 1960). In this case, the reward is a motivation for the employees to achieve the objectives. On the contrary, theory Z sees that employees are self – motivated to do their work and to achieve the objectives.

The three theories, X,Y (McGregor, 1960), and Z (Ouchi, 1980) bring a great implication toward the way how leaders/managers lead and manage the organization and the employees. On one hand, a leader who belongs to theory X will see employees negatively such as lazy, not motivated and apply authoritarian leadership styles, and on the other hand, a leader who belongs to theory Y will see employees positively such as willingness to work and have the capability and consequently a leader uses the participative leadership styles. While leaders who belong to the theory Z see employees as self-motivated, self-directed and therefore, the leaders are acting as a "coach" and allow the workers make the most decisions. Leaders who belong to X and Y would keep the power and authority to themselves. On contrary, leaders who belong to the theory Z see power and authority as a result of trust for the employees. Trusting the employees will result to trusting the leader. The power and authority comes from the workers' trust. Consequently, the managers/leaders allow the inputs of the workers in decision making (Abun, 2014).

Leadership styles are considered behavioral expressions of what they believe and what they know about their employees (Jordan, 2016). Favorableness or unfavorable attitude toward employees can have some effects on their leadership styles (Shahab, 2014). There have been no studies yet on the relationship between leadership attitude toward employees and leadership styles of leaders/manager and this is what we are going to investigate in the study. The output of the study will be used to provide information for the heads of different departments so that they know the effect of what they do on their employees. The study will contribute to the existing literature on leadership particularly on the effect of attitude toward leadership style.

The study is divided into five parts. The first part is the introduction in which it discusses the reason or rationale of the study and the purpose of the study. The second part is the review of the related literature. This part discusses the theories of the study based on different opinions of experts about leadership, attitude, and different leadership styles. The third part is a research methodology that discusses the research design, locale of the study, the population of the study, research procedures, research instruments, and statistical treatment of data. The fourth part is empirical data and analysis which discusses and analyses the data gathered through questionnaires. The fifth part is the result and discussion and conclusion.

II. Related Literature Review

The focus literature review is to find the ideas that have been presented in different books and journal articles related to the current investigation (McCombes, 2019). In the review of related literature, the researcher focuses on the literature that discusses the attitude and behavior and different leadership styles which are the variables to be investigated in the current study.

Theoretical and Conceptual background

The Concept of Leadership

Bennis and Nanus (2007) recognize that there are so many definitions of leadership that have been presented to the public and different authors present their understanding of leadership. Often these definitions are conflicting with each other and finally no common stand on what

leadership is and these definitions often time do not reflect the reality. Consequently, Wren (1995) contended that as a result of these conflicting concepts of leadership, it leads to the different focus of researchers in researching leadership. Some focused on personality, others focus on traits or others focus on behavior. However, despite the conflicting issues on the definition of leadership, Bennis (1959) define leadership as a process of influence in which the leader induces followers to behave in a desired manner. But what is the purpose of influencing followers to behave in a certain manner? This question leads to the essential characteristic of a leader which is the vision. A leader has a vision and this serves as the direction where he/she leads his/her people to and influences them to behave or to work in a particular way to achieve the vision (Nanus, 1995).

In line with what is defined by Nanus(1995), that leadership is a step by step process to implement a new sense of direction in the organization, Rauch and Behling (1984) define leadership as a “process of influencing of an organized group toward accomplishing its goals” (p.46). Similar to what Rauch and Behling (1984), Bass (1985), and Tichy and Devanna (1986) viewed leadership as transforming followers and creating a vision, and define ways to the followers on how to attain such vision. In other words, leaders are those who determine the direction of the organization and they lead and move people and the organization where they want to be (Tichy & Cohen, 2007). But Merton (1969) and Hogan and Curphy (1994) looked at leadership in terms of interpersonal relationships. It is the power to build an interpersonal relationship in which followers comply with the orders of leaders not because they have to but because they want to follow.

Based on these definitions, then we have three important aspects of leadership such as interpersonal relationships, influence, and goals. The term interpersonal means the relationship between leader and followers are not functional and transactional but interpersonal. The leaders treat followers as persons, not as objects and the relationship is subject to subject. Leaders should be able to develop interpersonal relationships with their employees. While the term influence means the power of the leader to affect others. This definition reflects the very essence of leadership to affect change. Lastly is the term goal. The purpose of influencing others or followers is to attain predetermined goals. There is no sense of leading if there is no direction or goal to be achieved. Therefore, the definition we adopt in this study is the definition given by Freiberg and Freil (1996) that leadership is a dynamic relationship between leader and followers based on mutual influence and common purpose in which both move to a higher level of motivation and moral development as they affect real, intended change.

Behavior explains the attitude

The concept of attitude has been confused with the concept of behavior. Often attitude refers to behavior and behavior refers to attitude. Both are two different properties but related to each other. In line with the topic of the study, investigating leadership attitude cannot proceed without knowing the theory of attitude. Only after understanding what attitude means, then one can understand the implication of such an attitude toward the behavior. The original inspiration of the study is the attitude theory and the attitude-behavior relation of Ajzen (1993) and also the theory of Allport about human Attitude and behavior. Understanding the attitude would allow us to understand human behavior and in this case, we would understand why leaders have different leadership styles even if they are within the same organization. Reading his work leads me to investigate the attitude of leaders toward their employees and how their attitude affects their leadership styles which are considered as a behavioral expression of their reactions toward the employees. According to Ajzen (1993), attitude is an “individual disposition to react with a certain degree of favorableness or unfavorableness to an object, behavior, person, institution or

event or any other discriminable aspect of the individual's world" (Ajzen, 1993, p.41). This individual disposition is a result of constant experience relating to that particular object or situation. After a person has been exposed to those particular objects, events, this person can form a certain attitude toward the object and such an attitude can be favorable or unfavorable to that particular object or event. The person may have positive or good ideas about the object or events and also he/she may have a negative idea about it depending on his/her experience. According to the theory of attitude-behavior relation, this attitude will affect the behavior of the person on what he/she will do next, though this idea had been challenged by Wicker (1969) that there is little correlation between attitude and behavior. Also, Dean (1958) had a similar finding with Wicker (1969) that there is no correlation between attitude and behavior when he studied the attitude toward labor unions and actual participation in a labor union meeting. However, Ajzen explains that such a result can be caused by other moderating variables such as self-monitoring as he cited from Snyder and Swann (1976), need for recognition, the confidence with which it is held, the circumstance surrounding the performance of the behavior. Align with the theory of Ajzen is Allport (1935). Though the definition of Ajzen (1993) is somewhat different from what Allport (1935) defined as the attitude there are similarities. Allport (1935) defined attitude as " a mental and neural state of readiness, organized through experience, exerting a directive or dynamic influence upon individual response to all objects and situations with which it is related" (p.810). The definition of Allport is similar to what Jung (1971) that attitude is the readiness of the mental or psychological state to react in a certain way. In my view, the definition of Allport, Jung, and the definition of Ajzen are similar, though the terms they use are different. These definitions are expressing the same point that attitude is an individual disposition toward objects or external stimuli. They all agreed that attitude is individual reactions or responses toward objects or events and these individual dispositions are the product of experience. Therefore it is not just an automatic reaction or response but it is a learned reaction of response. In other words, attitude is learned through direct experience with the object or events. However, Bandura, et.al (1961) made it explicit that attitude may be acquired not directly through direct experience but through observing others. Bandura took the example of how children learn, that they learn through observing people around them which are called models.

Based on Ajzen's (1993) theory of attitude, there are three dimensions of attitude and these are cognitive (knowledge), affective (feeling), and conative (behavioral aspect). Because of these three dimensions, the study of attitude and behavior is a multidimensional construct, not a single construct. Therefore, the investigation on the attitude-behavior relation must involve three dimensions. The cognitive dimension of attitude involves beliefs, knowledge, or thoughts the person has on the object of the attitude (McLeod, 2018). In short, it is the general knowledge of the person toward a particular object or event, people, or an institution. This general knowledge is acquired through experience whether is direct or indirect and a person can have positive or negative ideas about the object or event they encountered. The concern here is how much does a person knows about the object, event, person, or institution. The affective component refers to the emotional reaction toward that particular object, event, person, or institution. One can have a good feeling about the object, event, person, or institution, or a bad feeling depending on the experience or exposure of that person toward the object. Lastly is a behavioral or conative component of an attitude refers to the behavior of the person as a result of the feeling toward such an object, event, person, or institution (McLeod, 2018).

Leadership Attitude toward Employees

After we have discussed the concept of attitude and the concept of attitude-behavior relation, then we know what we mean when we discussed leadership attitude toward employees. Leadership attitude means the way how a leader looks or views the world around him or it is about what he/she thoughts and feels about the situation around him. Assumptions, thoughts, or views, and feelings can be both positive or good and negative or bad toward a particular object, event, person, or institution. Leadership attitude toward employees means that it is what leaders thought and feel about their employees. As we go back to the theory of attitude-behavior relation of Ajzen (1993), leadership attitude toward employees would affect the way how he/she will behave toward the employees he/she is leading. His assumptions, perception, thoughts, and feelings affect the way how he/she treats the employees.

Leadership attitude toward employees is the same as pointed by McGregor (1960) and Ouchi (1981). Now we look back to the theory X and Y of McGregor (1960) and theory Z of Ouchi (1981). According to McGregor (1960) leaders can be classified into two assumptions about employees which assumptions X and Assumption Y. On one hand, leaders who belong to X would assume or think that employees dislike work, dislike responsibility, and always find ways to avoid it. Consequently, this assumption or thought influences the leader or manager to apply coercion and control, and therefore leadership style would-be authoritarian. On the other hand, leaders who belong to Y would perceive or think that work is natural as play. Leaders who belong to this category believe that control and punishment are not the right way to motivate people to work. As long as they are motivated, they can direct their work. The concern of the management is to see to it that employees are satisfied because they believe that job satisfaction is a key factor to ensure employee commitment to work. This kind of leader will apply a participative leadership style. While theory Z of Ouchi (1981) argues that employees are innately self-motivated to work and they are loyal to the company and want to make the company succeed. Leaders who have this kind of view would trust their employees to do their job and leaders would be acting as coaches. Workers make the most decision and workers themselves are the ones to solve their conflict, while the leader or managers act as arbitrators. Managers/leaders who belong to this category allow the workers' ideas in making decisions and would focus on improving workers' well-being. This kind of leader would apply a democratic leadership style.

Leadership styles: authoritarian, participative, and delegative leadership

Leadership styles are the behavior of leaders dealing with their employees or followers. It is the way how they influence their followers to follow them and to perform their job to achieve organizational objectives. Porter- O'Grady (2003) as cited by Rodrigo (2012) defines leadership as a "multifaceted process of identifying goal or target, motivating other people to act and providing support and motivation to achieve a mutually negotiated goal" (para 2). From this definition, one should know that leadership has the vision to be accomplished, and to accomplish the vision, leaders use different approaches to support and motivate the followers to achieve the goal. Thus, leaders would use different leadership styles or different behavior to motivate their employees to carry out their job to achieve a common goal. This motivates many researchers to conduct studies to determine what kind of effective leadership style to motivate employees to work and to achieve the vision-mission and objectives. Early on, Lewin, et.al. (1939) conducted a study to determine different leadership styles and as a result, they identified three kinds of leadership behavior in dealing with their followers and they are authoritarian, participative, and delegative styles (**laissez-faire or free-rein**). **Greenleaf** (1977) base on his investigation, proposed a servant leadership style in which he proposed that leaders must

focus more on others than upon the self. A leader should not be motivated by self-interest but service to others. Conger and Kanungo (1988) propose a Charismatic leadership style in which they contend that to motivate people to work, leaders must have idealized goals to achieve and must have a strong personal commitment to achieving such a goal. They have to articulate this vision to their followers and set a high-performance expectation and motivate followers to achieve them. Burns (1978) develop transactional leadership. Burns suggested that leadership is a two-way process in which he argued that leaders should provide rewards in return for the subordinate's effort and performance. Providing rewards would be one of motivating employees to work smarter. The same person, Burns (1978) also proposed transformational leadership styles to motivate employees to work. But the work was done by Bass and Avolio (1996). Burns, Bass, and Avolio brought leadership to a higher level, to the level of morality. The concern is still the same on how to motivate employees to work. In the first place, he argued that a leader must be a role model for the employees particularly his values. Next is the inspirational motivation that provides a challenging goal for the employees to achieve. Then employees must be involved in discussing ideas on how to solve problems. Lastly is individualized consideration, in the sense that leaders should not generalize employees and treat them the same. Employees have different needs and want and problems and leadership should give attention to the different needs of individual employees. Many more theories that we cannot mention all here.

This study is not going to study all different leadership styles or leadership behavior. Based on the experience and observing what is going on in the leadership styles of the head of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region, the study focuses on authoritarian, participative, and delegative (*laissez-faire*) leadership styles. These leadership styles were discovered earlier but they may be still actual and relevant in the current context.

Authoritarian leadership style

This leadership style is also called an autocratic leadership style. This leadership style may be appropriate under certain circumstances but it may not be the rule. This style is also often called a dictatorial style. Autocratic leadership styles refer to leaders who provide the goal and methods to achieve the goal, then impose the deadline. He/she makes the decision and does not listen to the ideas coming from his/her employees (Cherry, 2019). Hard measures and close monitoring are often applied and punishment is a consequence when the employees fail to perform their works. This leadership style can work depending on the situation on the ground and depending on the nature of the job.

Participative leadership style/Democratic Leadership Style.

After more than 30 years of research, Rensis Likert (1967) discovered different leadership styles. The study was motivated by the desire to improve the workplace and how to motivate employees to perform in their job. He discovered four types of leadership styles and they are exploitative authoritative, benevolent authoritative, consultative, and participative styles. The idea of participative leadership styles is that the goal cannot be achieved by the leader alone without the participation of employees. This leadership style is marked by several practices such as the leader and the group collectively makes the decisions (Collective participative leadership) or, employees are invited to share ideas on the issue but at the end, it is the leader who will make the decision (democratic leadership) or the leader listens to the ideas of employees and then make the decision (autocratic participative leadership) or the leader allows the group to make a decision which is often time done through votes and the majority prevails (Janse, 2019)

Delegative Leadership style/ laissez-faire leadership style

William Ouchi (1981) propose theory Z of leadership style which is based on the assumption that workers are innately motivated to work and therefore let the employees do their job and the role of a leader is only to be a coach. Delegative leadership style is similar to that theory. Participative leadership styles allow the employees to exercise their authority to make decisions and to direct their job and the leader is not intervening. The leader takes a backseat when making a decision. This leadership style is also known as the laissez-faire (free-reign) leadership style. Though this leadership style has been criticized as the cause of productivity but such style may work in a particular situation (Cherry, 2019).

Conceptual Framework
Independent Variables

Dependent Variables

Source: Ajzen (1993) and Likert (1967)

Figure 1: The framework reflects the main concept of the study. It portrays the relationship between the independent variable (attitude toward employees) and the dependent variables (leadership styles).

Statement of the Problem

The study is to determine the correlation between the leadership attitude toward employees and the leadership styles applied by the head of offices in Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Region, particularly it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the leadership attitude of the office head toward employees in terms of
 - a. Cognitive attitude,
 - b. Affective attitude?
2. What is the leadership styles of office head of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of
 - a. Autocratic leadership style
 - b. Participative leadership style
 - c. Delegative leadership style
3. Is there a relationship between the leadership attitude toward employees and the leadership styles of office heads of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region?

Assumption of the Study

The study assumes that leadership attitude influence leadership styles of office head of Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Region. It is also assumed that leadership attitude and leadership styles are measurable.

Hypothesis

The theory of McGregor (1960) and Ouchi (1981) argue that leadership assumptions, leadership thoughts, and feeling about employees lead toward a certain approach of leadership or leadership style. Base on their idea, the current study hypothesizes that leadership attitude toward employees may correlate to the leadership styles of office heads.

Delimitation of the Study

The study covers only to measure leadership attitude toward employees and leadership styles of office head of Divine word Colleges in Ilocos Region. The study limits itself to measure autocratic leadership, participative, and delegative leadership styles.

III. Research Methodology

As scientific research, it follows certain methodology in its investigation. The study was carried out to find out the relationship between leadership attitude toward employees and leadership styles of office heads of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region. In carrying out the study proper research methodologies were followed particular research design, data gathering instruments, population, the locale of the study, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

The study used a descriptive assessment and correlational research design. Descriptive research refers to a research method that describes the population or phenomena being studied. It tries to answer the question of "what is" and not the "why question"(Bhat, 2019). It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situations, phenomena, or relationship variables. In short, it describes "what is" about the data (Ariola, 2006). While descriptive correlational research is to describe the variables and to discover relationships among variables and allow prediction of future events from present knowledge.

In line with the current study, the descriptive assessment and correlational method were deployed. The study determines the level of cognitive and affective leadership attitude toward employees and their correlation with the leadership styles of the office head. This was to determine the dominant leadership attitude of office heads and how such leadership attitude affects the leadership styles.

The locale of the Study

The locale of the study was the Divine Word College of Vigan. Divine Word College of Vigan is belonged to the Province of Ilocos Sur and is located within the heritage city of Vigan. Divine Word College of Vigan is run by the Congregation of the Divine Word Missionaries or known as Society of the Divine Word or in Latin, *Societas Verbi Divini* (SVD).

Population

The population of the study was composed of all office heads of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region. Since the total numbers of office heads are limited and therefore total enumeration is the sampling design of the study.

Data Gathering instruments

The study utilized validated questionnaires. For the leadership styles, the questionnaires (LSQ) were adapted from the work of Ntshingila (n.d) and for the leadership attitude, the questionnaires were constructed by the author based on the concept of leadership attitude of McGregor (1960) and Ouchi (1981) but validated through content validation and expert judgment. The classification of the attitude which is cognitive, affective, and conative is based on the concept of Ajzen (1993). On the leadership styles, questions number 1-6 are about authoritarian leadership styles, number 7-13 is about participative leadership styles and 14-18 is about delegative leadership styles.

Data Gathering Procedures

In the process of data gathering, the researcher sent a letter to the President of the College, requesting him to allow the researcher to flow his questionnaires in the college. The researcher personally met the President and students and requested them to answer the questionnaires. The retrieval of questionnaires was arranged between the President's representative and the researcher with the help of employees and faculty of the college.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In consistence with the study as a descriptive assessment and correlational research design, therefore descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were used. The weighted mean is used to determine the level of cognitive and affective leadership attitude of office heads toward employees and leadership styles. The Pearson r was used to measure the correlation of leadership attitudes toward employees and the leadership styles they apply in leading their schools.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Interpretation	Overall Descriptive Rating
4.21-5.00	<i>Strongly agree</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Somewhat agree</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Very Low/Very High</i>

IV. Empirical data and Analysis

Empirical data and analysis indicate that a study is an evidenced-based approach and the analysis is based on the data gathered through questionnaires or other kinds of research instruments. The study relies on real-world data and not on theories and concepts from the books without being supported by data (Tech Target, 2020). Based on this concept, this part presents data and interprets the data gathered through questionnaires. The presentation has based the arrangement of the statement of the problems.

- Problem1: What is the leadership attitude of office head toward employees in terms of**
- a. Cognitive attitude**
 - b. Affective attitude?**

Table 1: Cognitive Attitude n = 23

Statements	Composite Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. I know employees are capable of doing their work	4.13	A/H
2. I know most employees have the skills to perform their job	4.17	A/H
3. I know employees are willing to contribute to the attainment of the goals	4.35	A/H
4. Given the right environment, employees want to contribute ideas	4.17	A/H
5. I know employees are motivated to perform their work	4.17	A/H
Composite Mean	4.20	A/H

Source: Ajzen (1993) and McGregor (1960) and Ouchi (1981)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Strongly agree</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Somewhat agree</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Very Low/Very High</i>

As reflected in the data presented in the table, it shows that as a whole, the leadership attitude of office heads in terms of cognitive attitude gains a composite mean of 4.20 which is described as “agree or high” (A/H). It just means that the leadership attitude of office heads toward employees along with cognitive attitude is high but not very high and it is not also moderate, low, or very low. Even when they are taken separately, the data reveals that all items are rated within the same range of description which is "agree or high" such as they " know employees are capable of doing their work (4.13) and have the skills to perform their job (4.17), are willing to contribute to the attainment of the goals (4.35), motivated to perform their work (4.17) and given the right environment, employees want to contribute ideas” (4.17).

This rating demonstrates that leadership has a high degree of general knowledge about who their employees are. They know or believe that their employees are capable of performing their job, and have the necessary skills to do their job, are motivated to carry out their duties and responsibilities, and are willing to contribute ideas to help the organization. Harriss (2019) contends that trusting and knowing employees your employees can enhance employee engagement, increased productivity, and improve communication.

Table 2: Affective Attitude

Statements	Composite Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. I am happy that employees are doing their job	4.13	A/H
2. I feel good because employees have the skills to do their job	4.13	A/H
3. I am fortunate to work with employees who are willing to contribute to the attainment of the goals	4.22	A/H

4. I am just lucky to work with my employees who are motivated to work	4.22	A/H
5. I am always energized to receive new ideas from my employees	4.17	A/H
Composite Mean	4.17	A/H

Source: Source: Ajzen (1993) and McGregor (1960) and Ouchi (1981)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Strongly agree</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Somewhat agree</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Very Low/Very High</i>

As gleaned from the data, it shows that as a whole, the leadership attitude of office heads in terms of affective attitude obtains a composite mean of 4.17 which is interpreted as "agree or high" (A/H). Such rating demonstrates that the affective attitude of school heads toward employees in terms of affective attitude is high but not very high and it is not also moderate, low, or very low. Even if the items are taken singly, they all are rated within the same level of interpretation which is "agree or high" such as they "are happy that employees are doing their job (4.13), feeling good because employees have the skills to do their job (4.13), fortunate to work with employees who are willing to contribute to the attainment of the goals (4.22), feel lucky to work with employees who are motivated to work (4.22), and always energized to receive new ideas from employees" (4.17).

The composite mean manifests that there is a high and positive emotion of office heads toward the employees. The heads feel happy and energized because the employees are doing their job, having the skills to do their job, willing to contribute ideas to the attainment of goals, and motivated to work. The study of Rath (2004) published in Gallup business journal pointed out the effect of positive leadership which includes enhanced job satisfaction, greater work engagement, improved performance, and a more positive mood. This is also confirmed by the study of Pastor (2014) on the effect of leadership emotional intelligence. The study found that there is a correlation between the level of emotional intelligence of leaders and the professional performance of subordinates (Pastor, 2014).

Table 3: Summary Table on Attitude n = 23

Attitude	Composite Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Cognitive	4.20	A/H
Affective	4.17	A/H
Overall Mean	4.18	

Source: Ntshingila (n.d)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Strongly agree</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Somewhat agree</i>	<i>Moderate</i>

1.81-2.60 *Disagree* *Low/High*
1.00-1.80 *Strongly disagree* *Very Low/Very High*

The summary table shows that as a whole, the leadership attitude of office heads in terms of cognitive and affective attitude gains a composite mean of 4.18 which is described as "agree or high" (A/H). This concludes that the leadership attitude of office heads toward employees is high but not very high, and it is also not moderate, low, or very low. Taking them separately, both, cognitive and affective attitudes are perceived to be within the same interpretation which is "agree or high". This suggests that office heads have high ideas about their employees and have a high and positive feeling toward their employees.

Problem 2: What is the leadership styles of office head of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of

- 2.1. Autocratic leadership style***
- 2.2. Participative leadership style***
- 2.3. Delegative leadership style***

Table 4: Authoritarian Style

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Supervise the employees closely, or they are not likely to do their work	3.13	SWA/M
2. It is fair to say that most employees in the general population are lazy	2.30	SWA/M
3. As a rule, employees must be given rewards or punishment to motivate them to achieve organizational objectives	3.48	SWA/M
4. Most employees feel insecure about their work and need direction	2.96	SWA/M
5. The leader is the chief judge of the achievement of the employees	3.17	SWA/M
6. Effective leaders give orders and clarify procedures	3.87	
Composite Mean	3.15	SWA/M

Source: Ntshingila (n.d)

Legend:

<i>Range of Mean Values</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.51 – 5.00	<i>Strongly agree/Very High</i>
3.51 – 4.50	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.51 – 3.50	<i>Somewhat agree/Moderate extent</i>
1.51 – 2.50	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00 – 1.50	<i>Strongly disagree/Very low</i>

As gleaned from the data presented on the table, it appears that as a whole, the leadership style of office heads along with authoritarian style obtains a composite mean of 3.15 which is interpreted as “somewhat agree or moderate extent” (SWA/M). This composite mean points out that the authoritarian leadership style of the office head is not very high or high and it is also

not low or very low but to a moderate extent. This is also true when the items are taken separately which almost all items fall within the same level of interpretation which is “somewhat agree or moderate extent” such as “supervising the employees closely, or they are not likely to do their work (3.13), employees must be given rewards or punishment to motivate them to achieve organizational objectives (3.48), most employees feel insecure about their work and need direction (2.96), the leader is the chief judge of the achievement of the employees (3.17) and most employees in the general population are lazy (2.30).

The evaluation indicates that the office heads have a moderate level of authoritarian leadership style. The effect of authoritarian leadership style on employees may vary. For example, the study of Wang and Guan (2018) pointed out the positive effect of authoritarian leadership style on employees' performance in Chinese companies but there is also a study that found no correlation between authoritarian leadership style and performance because the subordinate of authoritarian leaders is not likely to follow an authoritarian leader (Wang, et.al., 2019).

Table 5: Democratic/participative Style

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
7. Leader wants to be part of the decision-making process	4.26	A/H
8. Guiding without pressure is the key to being a good leader	4.00	A/H
9. Leader wants frequent and supportive communication with the workers	4.22	A/H
10. Leaders need to help subordinates accept responsibility for completing their work	4.17	A/H
11. Leaders help subordinates find their “ passion”	3.74	A/H
12. Leader believes employees are competent and if given a task will do a good job	3.83	A/H
13. Leaders should let subordinates work problems out on their own	3.17	SWA/M
Composite Mean	3.85	

Source: Ntshingila (n.d)

Legend:

Range of Mean Values	Descriptive Interpretation
4.51 – 5.00	<i>Strongly agree/Very High</i>
3.51 – 4.50	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.51 – 3.50	<i>Somewhat agree/Moderate Extent</i>
1.51 – 2.50	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00 – 1.50	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

As pointed out in the data, it reveals that as a whole, the leadership style of office head along with democratic style receives a composite mean of 3.85 which is described as “agree or High” (A/H). This evaluation suggests that the participative leadership style of the office head is high but not very high and it is also not moderate, low, or very low. Even when the items are taken separately, it shows that all items are rated within the same level of interpretation which is "agree or high" such as, " wanting the employees to be part of decision-making (4.26), guiding

without pressure is the key to being a good leader (4.00), wanting frequent and supportive communication with the workers (4.22), helping subordinates accept responsibility for completing their work (4.17), helping subordinates find their “passion”(4.74), believing employees are competent and if given a task will do a good job (3.83), and letting the subordinates work problems out on their own (3.17).

The finding indicates that the democratic leadership style of the office head is high. Such democratic or participative leadership style can be seen in their effort to allow employees to participate in decision making, guide the employees without pressure, build supportive communication, help the employees to accomplish their task, help the employees to sustain their passion, believe in the capability of employees to do their task and let the employee do their task. Studies have pointed out the effect of democratic or participative leadership style. Dolly and Nonyelum (2018) have studied the effect of democratic or participative leadership style on the job performance of employees. The study found that participative or democratic leadership style improves the job performance of employees.

Table 6: laissez-faire/delegative leadership

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
14. Leadership requires staying out of the way of subordinates as they do their work	3.09	SWA/M
15. As a rule, a leader should allow subordinates to appraise their work	3.83	A/H
16. Leaders should give subordinates complete freedom to solve problems on their own	3.61	A/H
17. In most situations, workers prefer little input from the leader	3.17	SWA/M
18. In general, it is best to leave subordinates alone	2.78	SWA/M
Composite Mean	3.39	SWA/M

Source: Ntshingila (n.d)

Legend:

<i>Range of Mean Values</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.51 – 5.00	<i>Strongly agree</i>
3.51 – 4.50	<i>Agree</i>
2.51 – 3.50	<i>Somewhat agree</i>
1.51 – 2.50	<i>Disagree</i>
1.00 – 1.50	<i>Strongly disagree</i>

As presented on the table, the data manifest that as a whole the leadership style of office heads along with laissez-faire/delegative style obtains a composite mean of 3.39 which is described as “somewhat agree or moderate extent (SWA/M). It just means that the leadership styles of office heads in terms of laissez-faire/delegative style are not very high or high and it is also not low or very low but to a moderate extent. However, when the items are taken separately, three items were rated as somewhat agree or moderate extent such as, “leadership requires staying out of the way of subordinates as they do their work (3.09), in most situations, workers prefer little input from the leader (3.17), and in general, it is best to leave subordinates alone (2.78). In this case, leaders’ agreement on the statements is moderate. In other words, leaders do not

agree that they have to stay out of the way of subordinates' work and let employees do their things. There were two items in which the office heads agree that “a leader should allow subordinates to appraise their work (3.83), and leaders should give subordinates complete freedom to solve problems on their own” (3.61).

The result of the composite mean of 3.39 which means "somewhat agree or moderate" indicates that as a whole office heads do not agree or disagree with some practice of laissez-faire/delegative style of leadership. Their agreement on this style is moderate. Asrar-ul-Haq and Kuchinke (2016) pointed out in their study that laissez-faire leadership style showed a negative relationship with employee performance in terms of effectiveness and performance.

Table 7: Summary Table on Leadership Styles

Leadership Style	Composite Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Authoritarian	3.15	SWA/M
Participative/Democratic	3.85	A/H
Delegative/laissez-faire	3.39	SWA/M
Overall Mean	3.46	SWA/M

The summary table reveals that overall leadership style office heads obtain a composite mean of 3.46 which is interpreted as "somewhat agree or moderate"(SWA/M). It just means that the overall leadership style of office heads is not very high or high and it is not also low or very low but to a moderate extent. But taken the leadership styles singly, it shows that authoritarian style gained a composite mean of 3.15 and delegative/laissez-faire style obtained a composite mean of 3.39 which are interpreted as “somewhat agree. In other words, the heads do not really agree with the authoritarian and laissez-faire style, but they also do not disagree with the two styles of leadership and their agreement on these two styles is moderate. It is only participative or democratic leadership styles that the head of offices agree with (3.85).

From the finding, we can summarize that the office heads agree to practice the democratic leadership style but there can be some situations they can practice authoritarian and laissez-faire/delegative style of leadership.

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between the leadership attitude toward employees and the leadership styles of office heads of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region?

Table 8: Coefficients of correlation on the Relationship Between Leadership attitude and leadership styles

		Leadership
Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.018
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.933
	N	23

Overall, there is no correlation between Leadership

Based on the Pearson r Correlation, it reveals that overall there is no correlation between leadership attitude and leadership styles. But taking them singly, it shows that there is a significant relationship at 0.05 level (2-tailed) between affective attitude and leadership style,

particularly delegative/laissez-faire leadership style. There is a negative correlation of $-.442^*$ which means an inverse relationship; as X increases, Y decreases; as X decreases, Y increases. Negative correlation means

Table 9: Attitude and Different leadership styles

Leadership Style		Cognitive	Affective
Authoritarian	Pearson Correlation	.308	.047
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.153	.831
Participative	Pearson Correlation	.253	.077
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.244	.727
Delegative	Pearson Correlation	-.065	-.442*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.768	.035

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

V. Result and Discussion

The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship between the leadership attitude of office heads and their leadership styles. Based on the Pearson r Correlation, overall the study found no correlation between leadership attitude and the leadership style of the office head. It means that though the office heads know their employees either positive or negative, it does not necessarily affect their leadership style. Based on the data, the highest composited mean was obtained related to democratic leadership style which indicates that democratic leadership style is being highly applied as their leadership style, while authoritarian style and delegative or laissez-faire styles are moderately applied. It suggests that both leadership styles are applied depending on the situation.

Issues on leadership are still relevant to be discussed because it affects employees performance. Different leadership styles of managers impact the performance of employees. For example, the study of Asrar-ul-Haq (2016) pointed out the correlation between transformational leadership style and employee performance. Wang and Guan (2018) also found a positive correlation between authoritarian leadership styles and employee performance, though the study of Wang, et.al. (2019) found no correlation between authoritarian leadership and employee performance. The difference was explained by the fact that employees who are under authoritarian leaders are not likely to follow the authoritarian leader (wang, et.al. (2019). Dolly and Nonyelum (2018) had also presented similar findings regarding the impact of democratic leadership and employee performance. The study pointed out the democratic leadership style affects employees' productivity. In the case of laissez-faire or delegative leadership style, it affects a certain degree of role ambiguity and conflict, though it may not be significant (Al-Malki & Juan, 2018).

Applying the right kind of leadership will always be dependent on the situation. Thus, leadership is always situational or contextual, or contingency model (Fieldler, 1967). This theory argues that leadership does not exist in a vacuum but it is originated from the context (Oc, 2018). In other words, a leader should examine the context first before he/she can adopt a certain style of leadership. No leadership can be applied in all situations, though there can be one leadership style to be dominant as the current study found.

Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to investigate the impact of the leadership attitude of office heads and their leadership style. The study found that overall, the leadership attitude of office heads gained a composite mean of 4.18 which is described as "agree or high", and the leadership style of heads gained a composite mean of 3.46 which is considered as "somewhat agree or moderate level". When it comes to its correlation, the study found that overall, there is no correlation between leadership attitude and leadership style. It just means that their attitude toward employees does not affect their leadership style. This finding may contradict the early finding of McGregor (1960) Ouchi (1981) about theory X and Y and Z of Ouchi (1981). Therefore, the hypothesis of the study is rejected.

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